

This is a link to the data repository refubium, which hosts the experimental data and code used in the paper "Diode effect in Josephson junctions with a single magnetic atom" by Trahms, Martina; Melischek, Larissa; Steiner, Jacob F.; Mahendru, Bharti; Tamir, Idan; Bogdanoff, Nils; Peters, Olof; Reecht, Gael; Winkelmann, Clemens B.; von Oppen, Felix; Franke, Katharina J., published in Nature 615, 628 (2023).

<https://refubium.fu-berlin.de/handle/fub188/37348>